

THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT WATER THICKNESSES ON THE HEIGHT GROWTH OF RICE (ORYZA SATIVA)

Khojamkulova Yulduzoy Jahonkulovna

PhD, head of "Plant physiology and biochemistry" laboratory,
e-mail: yulduzoyxojamkulova@gmail.com

Rice Research Institute;

Allayorov O'rol Soat ugli

Allazov Otabek Chori ugli

Graduate students, Termiz Institute of
Agrotechnology and Innovative Development.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7781152>

Annotation. In this article, the rapid growth of plants, regardless of the change in rice growth stages, is mainly seen during the tillering and waxing stage, with a daily growth rate of 1,1-1,3 cm and it is reported that the height of the plants is the highest -106,9-121,6 cm when the water thickness is 5-15 cm in the paddy fields.

Key words: rice, "Iskandar", "Lazurniy", "Guljahon", water thickness, linear, stage, agricultural technology.

Introduction: To form a unified system of rice cultivation and its purchase on the scale of our country, rational use of land and water resources, as well as to fill the domestic consumer market with high-quality products, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2021 "On measures for the further development of rice cultivation" Decision № PD-4973 was adopted. Based on this decision, it is determined as an urgent task to use water-saving technologies in the field on a large scale, to plant 20% of the rice fields by seedling method, to level 50% with the help of laser equipment, and to implement rice seeds in modern planting devices on 30%. [1].

The level of study of the problem. In 2007, D.S. Magomedova conducted research in the Republic of Dagestan and found that the water thickness for rice cultivation is 5 cm thick from germination to the end of the tillering stage, and 15-20 cm in the following stages gives the best results and it was noted that the one-year weed contamination of the rice paddy could be reduced up to 2-3 times, and when watered at this depth, 16-18 thousand cubic meters of water per hectare can be used and 62.5 centners of grain yield per hectare can be obtained. [2]

Sande Teman Abu planted Liman and Lider varieties of rice in the condition of Krasnodar Territory in 2006, studied the effect of water thickness and nitrogen fertilizing rates on the productivity of those varieties and

recommended agrotechnics of continuously flooded rice cultivation for production. [3].

Rice height growth is a complex process that has its distinct aspects. These signs mainly depend on the natural heredity of the variety, the level of environmental, agrotechnical and external factors. Rice grows very slowly in its early stages (germination, tillering). The growth process is accelerated from the booting stage to the flowering stage.

The most rapid growth continues until 10-15 days before the beginning of the wax ripening stage. In the data of N.N. Silanteva (1991), the growth of rice height is the same despite the background of mineral fertilizers given in different amounts during the stage of full germination of rice, the growth of rice height during this stage is only due to the reserves of nutrients in the endosperm part of the seed, and only in some cases it depends on the natural fertility of the soil. [4].

Research aim. It consists of planting 3 early-early "Guljahon", mid-early "Iskandar" and late-early "Lazurniy" rice varieties in the field and studying the effect of 5, 10, 15 and 20 cm water thicknesses on the height of rice varieties.

Research methods. It was carried out on the basis of methodological manuals such as "Methods of conducting field experiments", "Methodology of field experiments" (B.A. Dospekhov, 1985) and "Rice cultivation in Uzbekistan up to the height of water-saving use (2019) methodical instructions" [5].

The height of the "Guljahon" rice variety in the germination stage was 14.2 cm, 54.0 cm in the tillering stage, 93.1 cm in the booting stage, and 110.9 cm in the wax ripening stage while there was 5 cm of water in the paddy fields. When the water thickness was 10 cm, the germination stage was 14.3 cm, the tillering stage was 55.6 cm, the booting stage was 98.9 cm, and the wax ripening stage was 112.3 cm. When the water thickness was 15 cm, the germination stage was 14.9 cm, the tillering stage was 58.6 cm, the booting stage was 100.8 cm, and the wax ripening stage was 116.2 cm. In paddy fields, when the water depth was 20 cm, it was 16.5 cm during the germination stage, 56.1 cm during the tillering stage, 99.6 cm during the booting stage, and 113.8 cm during the wax ripening stage.

In the "Guljahon" variety of rice, rapid growth was observed between growth stages, mainly during the tillering and wax ripening stages, and it was found that the daily growth rate was 1.2-1.3 cm (see Table 1).

Table 1

The effect of different water thicknesses on the height of rice varieties, sm

Options	Water thickness	Growth stages			
		Germination	Tillering	Booting	Wax ripening
"Guljahon"					
1	5 SM	14,2	54,0	93,1	110,9
2	10 SM	14,3	55,6	98,9	112,3
3	15 SM	14,9	58,6	100,8	116,2
4	20 SM	16,5	56,1	99,6	113,8
"Iskandar"					
1	5 SM	14,4	56,3	99,3	114,3
2	10 SM	14,6	60,2	103,6	118,1
3	15 SM	14,9	63,6	106,9	121,6
4	20 SM	16,7	60,7	103,0	118,7
"Lazurniy"					
1	5 SM	14,0	52,9	98,2	110,6
2	10 SM	14,3	53,6	90,9	112,8
3	15 SM	14,9	60,8	103,4	116,5
4	20 SM	16,2	54,2	100,7	114,1

In "Iskandar" variety of rice, when the depth of water in the rice fields was 5 cm, the height of the plants was 14.4 cm during the germination stage, 56.3 cm during the tillering stage, 99.3 cm during the booting stage, and 114.3 cm during the wax ripening stage. When the water thickness was 10 cm, it was 14.6 cm in the stage of germination, 60.2 cm in the tillering, 103.6 cm in the stage of tube formation, and 118.1 cm in the stage of wax ripening. In rice planted areas, when the water depth was 15 cm, the height of plants during germination was 14.9 cm, during the stage of tillering, it was 63.6 cm, during the stage of booting, it was 106.9 cm, and during the wax ripening stage, it was 121.6 cm.

When the water thickness was increased by 20 cm, it was 16.7 cm in the stage of germination, 60.7 cm in the stage of tillering, 103.0 cm in the stage of tube formation or booting, and 118.7 cm in the stage of wax ripening. In "Iskandar" variety, it was observed that the rate of daily growth was 1.1-1.3 cm.

The "Lazurniy" rice variety grew to a height of 14.0 cm at the germination stage, 52.9 cm during tillering stage, 98.2 cm at the booting stage, and 110.6 cm during the wax ripening stage. When the water thickness in rice fields was kept at 10 cm, the plants attained 14.3 cm during germination, 53.6 cm during tillering, 90.9 cm during booting, and 112.8 cm during wax ripening. When the water thickness was 15 cm, it was 14.9 cm in the germination stage, 60.8 cm in

the tillering stage, 103.4 cm in the booting stage, and 111.5 cm in the wax ripening stage. When the water thickness increased by 20 cm, it was 16.2 cm in the germination, 54.2 cm in the stage of tillering, 100.7 cm in the stage of booting, and 114.1 cm in the stage of wax ripening.

By the time of the full tillering of the plants, several differences between the variants emerged, and the height of the plants was up to 7.9 cm higher in the variants with water thickness of 5-15 cm compared to the other variants.

So, all the early-ripe "Guljahon", mid-ripe "Iskandar" and late-ripe "Lazurnyy" rice varieties are the highest in terms of height - when the water thickness in the fields planted with small rice is 15 cm, it is observed during the wax ripening stage of the plants and it was 116,2 cm in the "Guljahon" rice variety, "Iskandar" variety was 121.6 cm, and the "Lazurniy" variety was 111,5 cm.

Conclusions: In the "Guljahon" variety of rice, rapid growth was observed between growth stages, mainly during the tillering and wax ripening stages, and it was found that the daily growth rate was 1.2-1.3 cm. In the "Iskandar" variety as well, rapid growth was observed between the booting and wax ripening growth stages, and the daily growth rate was 1.1-1.3 cm. By the time of the full tillering of the plants, several differences between the variants emerged, and the height of the plants was up to 7.9 cm higher in the variants with water thickness of 5-15 cm compared to the other variants.

References:

1. Decision PD-4973 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of February 2, 2021 "On measures to further develop rice cultivation".
2. Magomedova. D.S Optimization of rice irrigation regime in Dagestan. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of candidate of agricultural sciences. Makhachkala 2007
3. Sonde Teman Abu. Features of the irrigation regime and nitrogen nutrition of rice varieties cultivated on meadow-chernozem soils of the North Caucasus. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of candidate of agricultural sciences. Krasnodar 2006
4. Silantieva.N.N. Triticale as an intermediate crop in rice crop rotation. Abstract diss. Cand. agricultural sciences. Tashkent. 1991. p.5.
5. Sattarov M.A., Ergashev M.A., Otamirzaev N.G', Kalandarov B.I., M. Khaitov. "Recommendation on how to save water for rice cultivation in Uzbekistan". Tashkent 2019. p. 6-7.